

NONLINEAR CONTROL THEORY AND CHAOTIC DYNAMICAL SYSTEMS

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Abstract. The main purpose of this paper is to treat the role of multiparameters in the existence of solutions of highly-coupled nonlinear dynamical systems and numerical computation of solutions.

INTRODUCTION

Consider nonlinear dynamical systems of the form:

$$\begin{cases} E(t, \theta, x) \frac{dx}{dt} = A(t, \theta, x)x + B(t, \theta, x)u \\ y = C(t, \theta, x)x + D(t, \theta, x)u \end{cases} \quad (1.0)$$

where $\theta = (\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_n)$ is a multiparameter and A, B, C, D, E are nonlinear operators, where x is a state vector, u is an input vector and y is an output vector. The basic problems involved are the stabilization, reducibility, uncoupling of the nonlinear system, construction of feedback law for controls, the questions of observability and time-estimation of certain operations on the dynamical system to carry out certain time dependent reactions due to parameter changes $\theta = (\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_n)$. Time-dependent nonlinear systems require more delicate estimates and monitoring than in the cases of linearized control systems. Hence parallel processing of computer algorithms is required. In the cases of CAD/CAM and robotics particularly, much more precision must be obtained by the numerical algorithms than in cases of the linearized control theory approach.

Examples of the above type systems are given for classes of such systems

where distributed parameters are used to give more robustness of feedback control laws which may anticipate systems with an unusual behavior which may occur under certain circumstances. Certainly one desires to avoid chaotic systems in some applications and also needs to recognize the nature of such systems which may become chaotic under certain conditions.

Example (Method I).

Consider dynamical systems of the form:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{N}_1 = N_1 - N_1^2 - \alpha N_1 N_2 - \beta N_1 N_3 \\ \dot{N}_2 = N_2 - \beta N_2 N_1 - N_2^2 - \alpha N_2 N_3 \\ \dot{N}_3 = N_3 - \alpha N_3 N_1 - \beta N_3 N_2 - N_3^2 \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

where α, β are parameters. The role of α, β will be seen to be important in determining whether such type systems may be uncoupled, and also in determining the actual existence of a solution of such a system.

Let $D = \frac{d}{dt}$ and also where $N_1 N_2 N_3 \neq 0$

$$\begin{pmatrix} U \\ V \\ W \end{pmatrix} \triangleq \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ N_2 & N_3 & N_1 \\ 0 & 0 & N_1 N_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} N_1 \\ N_2 \\ N_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.2)$$

then

$$DU = DN_1 + DN_2 + DN_3$$

$$DU = [N_1 + N_2 + N_3] - [N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2] \\ + (-\alpha - \beta) [N_1 N_2 + N_2 N_3 + N_1 N_3]$$

$$DU = U - [N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2] + (-\alpha - \beta)V$$

Now

$$U^2 = [N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2] + 2[N_1 N_2 + N_2 N_3 + N_3 N_1]$$

$$U^2 = [N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2] + 2V$$

and

$$DU = U - U^2 + 2V + (-\alpha - \beta)V \quad (1.3)$$

$$DU = U - U^2 + (2 - \alpha - \beta)V$$

Now

$$W \triangleq N_1 N_2 N_3$$

and

$$DW = (N_2 N_3)DN_1 + (N_1 N_2)DN_2 + (N_2 N_1)DN_3$$

$$DW = N_2 N_3 [N_1 - N_1^2 - \alpha N_1 N_2 - \beta N_1 N_3]$$

$$+ N_1 N_3 [N_2 - \beta N_2 N_1 - N_2^2 - \alpha N_2 N_3]$$

$$+ N_2 N_1 [N_3 - \alpha N_3 N_1 - \beta N_3 N_2 - N_3^2]$$

$$DW = (N_1 N_2 N_3) - N_1 (N_1 N_2 N_3) - \alpha N_2 (N_1 N_2 N_3)$$

$$- \beta N_3 (N_1 N_2 N_3) + (N_1 N_2 N_3)$$

$$- \beta N_1 (N_1 N_2 N_3) - N_2 (N_1 N_2 N_3)$$

$$- \alpha N_3 (N_1 N_2 N_3) + (N_1 N_2 N_3)$$

$$- \alpha N_1 (N_1 N_2 N_3) - \beta N_2 (N_1 N_2 N_3)$$

$$- N_3 (N_1 N_2 N_3)$$

$$DW = 3W + (-1 - \alpha - \beta)N_1 W + (-1 - \alpha - \beta)N_2 W \\ + (-1 - \alpha - \beta)N_3 W$$

$$DW = 3W + (-1 - \alpha - \beta)WU \quad (1.4)$$

Next,

$$V \triangleq N_1 N_2 + N_2 N_3 + N_3 N_1$$

$$U \triangleq N_1 + N_2 + N_3$$

$$UV = N_1^2 N_2 + (N_1 N_2 N_3) + N_1^2 N_3 + N_2^2 N_1 + N_2^2 N_3 \\ + (N_1 N_2 N_3) + (N_1 N_2 N_3) + N_2 N_3^2 + N_1 N_3^2$$

and

$$UV = 3W + [N_1^2 N_2 + N_1 N_2^2 + N_3 N_2^2 + N_2 N_3^2] \\ + N_1^2 N_3 + N_1 N_3^2 \quad (1.5)$$

Now

$$DV = N_2 DN_1 + N_1 DN_2 + N_2 DN_3 + N_3 DN_2 + N_1 DN_3 \\ + N_3 DN_1$$

$$DV = N_2 N_1 - N_1^2 N_2 - \alpha N_1 N_2^2 - \beta (N_1 N_2 N_3)$$

$$+ N_1 N_2 - \beta N_1^2 N_2 - N_1 N_2^2 - \alpha (N_1 N_2 N_3)$$

$$+ N_2 N_3 - \alpha (N_1 N_2 N_3) - \beta N_2 N_3^2 - N_2 N_3^2$$

$$+ N_3 N_2 - \beta (N_3 N_2 N_1) - N_3 N_2^2 - \beta N_2 N_3^2$$

$$+ N_1 N_3 - \alpha N_3 N_1^2 - \beta (N_1 N_2 N_3) - N_1 N_3^2$$

$$+ N_3 N_1 - N_3 N_1^2 - \alpha (N_1 N_2 N_3) - \beta N_1 N_3^2$$

$$DV = 2V + (-3\alpha - 3\beta)W$$

$$+ [-N_1^2 N_2 - \alpha N_1 N_2^2] +$$

$$[-\beta N_1^2 N_2 - N_1 N_2^2] +$$

$$[-N_3 N_2^2 - \alpha N_2 N_3^2] +$$

$$[-\alpha N_3 N_1^2 - N_1 N_3^2] +$$

$$[-\beta N_2^2 N_3 - N_2 N_3^2] +$$

$$[-N_3 N_1^2 - \beta N_1 N_3^2]$$

Now

$$DV = 2V + (-3\alpha - 3\beta)W +$$

$$-\alpha [N_1 N_2^2 + N_2 N_3^2 + N_1^2 N_3]$$

$$-\beta [N_1 N_3^2 + N_2 N_3^2 + N_1^2 N_2] +$$

$$-1 [N_1^2 N_2 + N_3^2 N_1^2 + N_1 N_2^2 + N_3 N_2^2$$

$$+ N_1 N_3^2 + N_2 N_3^2]$$

Now

$$UV = 3W +$$

$$[N_1^2 N_2 + N_1^2 N_3 + N_2^2 N_1 + N_2^2 N_3 + N_2 N_3^2 + N_1 N_3^2]$$

and

$$DV = 2V + (-3\alpha - 3\beta)W +$$

$$\left\{ -\alpha [N_1 N_2^2 + N_2 N_3^2 + N_1^2 N_3] \right.$$

$$\left. -\beta [N_1 N_3^2 + N_2 N_3^2 + N_1^2 N_2] \right\}$$

$$+ \{3W - UV\}$$

and finally

$$DV = 2V + (3 - 3\alpha - 3\beta)W - UW \quad (1.7)$$

$$+ \left\{ -\alpha [N_1 N_2^2 + N_2 N_3^2 + N_1^2 N_3] \right.$$

$$\left. -\beta [N_1 N_3^2 + N_2 N_3^2 + N_1^2 N_2] \right\}$$

Now we have the following equations:

$$DU = U - U^2 + (2 - \alpha - \beta)V \quad (1.3)$$

$$DW = 3W + (-1 - \alpha - \beta)WU \quad (1.4)$$

$$DV = 2V + (3 - 3\alpha - 3\beta)W - UW \quad (1.5)$$

$$+ \left\{ -\alpha [N_1 N_2^2 + N_2 N_3^2 + N_1^2 N_3] \right.$$

$$\left. -\beta [N_1 N_3^2 + N_2 N_3^2 + N_1^2 N_2] \right\}$$

Thus for a choice of $\alpha = \beta$

$$DV = 2V + (3 - 3\alpha - 3\alpha)W - UW$$

$$-\alpha [N_1 N_2^2 + N_2 N_3^2 + N_1^2 N_3 + N_1 N_3^2$$

$$+ N_2 N_3^2 + N_1^2 N_2]$$

and

$$DV = 2V + (3 - 3\alpha - 3\alpha)W - UW - \alpha [UV - 3W]$$

finally

$$DV = 2V + (3 - 6\alpha)W - UW - \alpha [UV - 3W]$$

and

$$DV = 2V + (3 - 6\alpha)W - UW - \alpha UV + 3\alpha W$$

$$DV = 2V + 3W - 6\alpha W - UW - \alpha UV + 3\alpha W$$

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} DV &= 2V + (3 - 3\alpha)W - UW + (-\alpha UV) \\ DU &= U - U^2 + (2 - 2\alpha)V \\ DW &= 3W + (-1 - 2\alpha)WU \end{aligned} \right. \quad (1.8)$$

for $\alpha = \beta$ and for $\alpha = 1$, we can solve for $U(t)$, then $W(t)$, and then finally for $V(t)$.

Method II ($\alpha = \beta = 1$)

$$\begin{cases} \dot{N}_1 = N_1 - N_1^2 - N_1 N_2 - N_1 N_3 \\ \dot{N}_2 = N_2 - N_2 N_1 - N_2^2 - N_2 N_3 \\ \dot{N}_3 = N_3 - N_3 N_1 - N_3 N_2 - N_3^2 \end{cases}$$

Let $D = \frac{d}{dt}$ and

$$\begin{cases} u \triangleq (N_1 + N_2 + N_3) \\ v \triangleq (N_1 + \omega N_2 + \omega^2 N_3) \\ w \triangleq (N_1 + \omega^2 N_2 + \omega N_3); \quad \omega^4 = \omega \end{cases}$$

where $\omega^3 - 1 = (\omega - 1)(\omega^2 + \omega + 1) = 0$. Then

$$Du = [DN_1 + DN_2 + DN_3]$$

$$Du = [N_1 - N_1^2 - N_1 N_2 - N_1 N_3]$$

$$+ [N_2 - N_2 N_1 - N_2^2 - N_2 N_3]$$

$$+ [N_3 - N_3 N_1 - N_3 N_2 - N_3^2]$$

$$Du = u - (N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2) - 2(N_1 N_2 + N_2 N_3 + N_3 N_1)$$

$$vw = (N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2) - (N_1 N_2 + N_2 N_3 + N_3 N_1)$$

$$u^2 = (N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2) + 2(N_1 N_2 + N_2 N_3 + N_3 N_1)$$

$$Du + u^2 = u; \quad Du = u - u^2$$

Now

$$\begin{cases} 2vw = 2(N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2) - 2(N_1 N_2 + N_2 N_3 + N_3 N_1) \\ Du = u - (N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2) - 2(N_1 N_2 + N_2 N_3 + N_3 N_1) \end{cases}$$

so

$$Du - 2vw = u - 3(N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2)$$

$$\begin{cases} vw = (N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2) - (N_1 N_2 + N_2 N_3 + N_3 N_1) \\ u^2 = (N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2) + 2(N_1 N_2 + N_2 N_3 + N_3 N_1) \end{cases}$$

so

$$(u^2 - vw) = 3(N_1 N_2 + N_2 N_3 + N_3 N_1)$$

and

$$\frac{(u^2 - vw)}{3} = (N_1 N_2 + N_2 N_3 + N_3 N_1)$$

also

$$(2vw + u^2) = 3(N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2)$$

and

$$\left(\frac{2vw + u^2}{3}\right) = (N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2)$$

Then

$$Du = u - \left(\frac{2vw + u^2}{3}\right) - 2\left(\frac{u^2 - vw}{3}\right)$$

$$Du = u - \frac{4}{3} u^2$$

$$v = N_1 + \omega N_2 + \omega^2 N_3$$

$$Dv = DN_1 + \omega DN_2 + \omega^2 DN_3$$

$$Dv = [N_1 - N_1^2 - N_1 N_2 - N_1 N_3]$$

$$+ [\omega N_2 - \omega N_2 N_1 - \omega N_2^2 - \omega N_2 N_3]$$

$$+ [\omega^2 N_3 - \omega^2 N_3 N_1 - \omega^2 N_3 N_2 - \omega^2 N_3^2]$$

$$Dv = (N_1 + \omega N_2 + \omega^2 N_3) + (-N_1^2 - \omega N_2^2 - \omega^2 N_3^2) \\ + (-1 - \omega) N_1 N_2 + (-\omega - \omega^2) N_2 N_3 \\ + (-1 - \omega^2) N_3 N_1$$

$$Dv = v + (-N_1^2 + \omega N_2^2 + \omega^2 N_3^2) \\ + (\omega^2 N_1 N_2 + N_2 N_3 + \omega N_3 N_1)$$

$$Dv = v - uv$$

$$w = N_1 + \omega^2 N_2 + \omega N_3$$

$$Dw = DN_1 + \omega^2 DN_2 + \omega DN_3$$

$$Dw = [N_1 - N_1^2 - N_1 N_2 - N_1 N_3] \\ + [\omega^2 N_2^2 - \omega^2 N_2 N_1 - \omega^2 N_2^2 - \omega^2 N_2 N_3] \\ + [\omega N_3 - \omega N_3 N_1 - \omega N_3 N_2 - \omega N_3^2]$$

$$Dw = [N_1 + \omega^2 N_2 + \omega N_3] + [-N_1^2 - \omega^2 N_2^2 - \omega N_3^2] \\ + (-1 - \omega^2) N_2 N_1 + (-\omega^2 - \omega) N_3 N_2 \\ + (-1 - \omega) N_3 N_1$$

$$Dw = [N_1 + \omega^2 N_2 + \omega N_3] - [N_1^2 + \omega^2 N_2^2 + \omega N_3^2] \\ + [\omega N_2 N_1 + \omega N_3 N_2 + \omega^2 N_3 N_1]$$

$$Dw = w - wu$$

SUMMARY

The main purpose of this work is to develop methods applicable to control of

highly coupled nonlinear dynamical systems containing multiparameters which may have a chaotic behavior. Due to the loss of components of a nonlinear dynamical system it may have a chaotic solution instead of a stable controllable observable solution.

The basic mathematics involved in such nonlinear multiparameter systems is treated so as to make sufficient changes in the system without losing the system completely as far as applications are concerned. This requires the development of time-dependent multiple objective numerical algorithms involving time to accomplish various desired maneuvers.

Results obtained in this paper can be used to establish feedback control laws for nonlinear dynamical systems of the form:

$$E(t, \theta, x) \frac{dx}{dt} = A(t, \theta, x)x + B(t, \theta, x)u$$

$$y = C(t, \theta, x)x + D(t, \theta, x)u$$

where $\theta = (\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_n)$ is a multiparameter and A, B, C, D, E are nonlinear operators, where x is a state vector, u is an input vector and y is an output vector. The basic problems which must be considered are the stabilization, reducibility, uncoupling of the nonlinear system, construction of feedback law for controls, the questions of observability and time-estimation of certain operations on the dynamical system to carry out certain time dependent actions and reactions due to parameter changes $\theta = (\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_n)$.

Time dependent nonlinear systems require more delicate estimates and monitoring than the cases of linearized control systems. Hence, parallel processing of computer algorithms is required. In the cases of CAD/CAM and robotics particularly, much more precision must be obtained by the numerical algorithms than in cases of the linearized control theory approach.

Examples of the above type systems are given for classes of such systems

where distributed parameters are used to give more robustness of feedback control laws which may anticipate systems with an unusual behavior which may be required under certain circumstances. Certainly one desires to avoid chaotic systems used in practical applications and one also needs to recognize the chaotic nature of such systems which may become chaotic under certain conditions. Other results along these topics will appear shortly elsewhere.